

IN-SILICO CHARACTERIZATION OF TOLUENE DIOXYGENASE FROM TOLUENE DEGRADING *PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA*Nadia Hussain¹, Saboor Muarij Bunny², Amal H. I. Al Haddad³, Riffat Iqbal⁴, Fatima Muccee⁵, Aleena Ahmad Khan⁶

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Abstract

Toluene due to the associated health hazards and persistent nature has been declared a carcinogenic pollutant. Its mitigation from environmental sources is the major issue. Several toluene remediating bacteria have been reported which possess wide range of toluene degradation enzymes. To fully exploit the potential of these bacteria, there is need to get insights into these enzymes. Current study was initiated to characterize the toluene 4-monooxygenase (T4MO) enzyme from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Initially, sequences of six subunits. i. e., TmoA, TmoB, TmoC, TmoD, TmoE and TmoF were retrieved from Uniprot database. These sequences were analyzed through different tools like PROTPARAM, SOPMA, ALPHAFOLD protein database and MEME SUITE. Analysis revealed the physicochemical attributes of components of enzymes as follows; number of amino acids (84-500), molecular weight (58103.54-9587.99), pI (4.38-5.57), aliphatic index (66.80-95.73) and GRAVY (-0.114-0.637). Secondary (2D) structure investigation demonstrated the alpha helix, extended strand and random coil ranging between 6-291, 74-6 and 194-34, respectively. TmoA and E subunits exhibited the highest level of complex folding. All the subunits were found to contain conserved motifs. Current study findings might be used for engineering of the enzyme using gene manipulation techniques in order to exploit its potential optimally.

2.2 Prediction of physicochemical attributes: PROTPARAM TOOL

To predict the physical and chemical properties of T4MO components documented in current study, EXPASY PROTPARAM TOOL (Available at <http://web.expasy.org/protparam/>, accessed on April 2025) was consulted (Garg et al. 2016). Tool helped in analyzing the parameters like number of amino acids, molecular weight, isoelectric point (pI), instability and aliphatic index and Grand Average of Hydropathicity (GRAVY). Input was provided as single letter code based protein sequence in FASTA format.

2.3 Prediction of secondary (2D) configuration: SOPMA TOOL

SOPMA Secondary Structure Prediction Method (Available at https://npsa-prabi.ibcp.fr/cgi-bin/npsa_automat.pl?page=/NPSA/npsa_sopma.html, accessed on April 2025) (Geourjon and Deleage 1995). The input was provided as single letter code based protein sequence in FASTA format by selecting the output width of 70, number of conformations (4). i. e., helix, sheet, turn and coil. Similarity threshold was 8 and window width was 17.

2.4 Prediction of three (3D) configuration: ALPHAFOLD

ALPHAFOLD Protein Structure Database (Available at <https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk>, accessed on April 2025) (Varadi et al. 2022). This database is based on AI system and is used to determine the 3D configuration of protein using amino acid sequence.

2.5 Prediction of conserved motifs: MEME SUITE Motif Based Sequence Based Analysis Tool, The MEME SUITE (Available at <https://meme-suite.org/meme/tools/meme>, accessed on April 2025) (Nystrom and McKay 2021). This tool is employed to determine the fixed length patterns of ungapped novel motifs of proteins. For this analysis, classic mode of motif discovery was selected and sequence was Typed in as single letter code based amino acid sequence. For motif site distribution in sequences, Any Number of Repetitions (anr) was choosen. Number of motifs was 3. Each predicted motif was split into 2/3 sequences, each with separate p-values and single E-value, Motifs locations were provided in the form of diagramme with p-value.

3. Results

3.1 Sequences of T4MO enzyme components

IDs, accession numbers and sequences of subunits of T4MO enzyme. i. e., TmoA, TmoB, TmoC, TmoD, TmoE and TmoF, are described in detail in Table 1.

Table 1: Components of toluene 4-monooxygenase (T4MO), their Uniprot accession IDs and sequences

Enzyme subunit	Accession #	Sequence
Hydroxylase component subunit α (TmoA)	Q00456	MAMHPRKDWYELTRATNWTPSYVTEEQFLPERMS
		GHMGIPLEKWESYDEPYKTSYPEYVSIQREKDAGA
		YSVKAALERAKIYENS DPGWISTLKSHYGAI AVGEY
		AAVTGEGRMARFSKAPGNRNMATFGMMDEL RHG
		QLQLFFPHEYCKKDRQFDWAWRAYHSNEWAAIAA
		KHFFDDIITGRDAISVAIMLTFSFETGFTNMQFLGLAA
		DAAEAGDYTFANLISSIQTDESRHAQQGGPALQLLIE
		NGKREEAQKKVDMAIWRAWRLFAVLTGPVMDYYT

		<p>PLEDRSQSFKEFMYEWIIGQFERSLIDLGLDKPWYWD LFLKDIDELHHSYHMGVWYWRTTAWWNPAAGVTP EERDWLEEKYPGWNKRWGRCWDVITENVLNDRMD LVSPETLPSVCNMSQIPLVGVPGDDWNIEVFSLEHNG RLYHFGSEVDRWVVFQQDPVQYQNHMNIVDRFLAGQ IQPMTLEGALKYMGFQSIEEMGKDAHDFAWADKCK PAMKKS</p>
Hydroxylase component subunit Y (TmoB)	Q00457	<p>MSAFPVHAAFEKDFLVQLVVVDLNDSDQVAEKVA YHCVNRRVAPREGVMRVRKHRSTELFPRDMTIAESG LNPTEVIDVVFEE</p>
Ferredoxin componeny (TmoC)	Q00458	<p>MSFEKICSLDDIWVGEMETFETSDGTEVLIVNSEEHG VKAYQAMCPHQEILLSEGSYEGGVITCRAHLWTFND GTGHGINPDDCCCLAEYPVEVKGDDIYVSTKGILPNKA HS</p>
Effector component (TmoD)	Q00459	<p>MSTLADQALHNNNVGPIIRAGDLVEPVIETAEIDNPG KEITVEDRRAYVRIAAEGELILTRKTLEEQLGRPFNM QELEINLASFAGQIQADEDQIRFYFDKTM</p>
Ferredoxin reductase (TmoE)	Q00460	<p>MSFESKKPMRTWSHLAEMRKKPSEYDIVSRKLHYST NNPDSPWELSPDSPMNLWYKQYRNASPLKHDNWD FTDPDQLVYRTYNLMQDGQESYVQSLFDQFNEREHD QMVREGWEHTMARCYSPLRYLFHCLQMSSAYVQQM APASTISNCCILQTADSLRWLTHHTAYRTHELSLTYPDA GLGEHERELWEKEPGWQGLRELMEKQLTAFDWGEAF VSLNLVVKPMIVESIFKPLQQQAWENNDTLLPLLIDSQL KDAERHSRWSKALVKHALENPDNHAVIEGWIEKWRPL ADRAAEAYLSMLSSDILPAQYLERSTSLRASILTV</p>

<p>ferredoxin-NAD(+) reductase component (TmoF)</p>	<p>Q03304</p>	<p>MFNIQSDDLHHEADSNDTLLSAALRAELVFPYECNS GGCGACKIELLEGEVSNLWPDAPGLAARELRKNRFLA CQCKPLSDLKIKVINRAEGRASHPPKRFSTRVVSKRFLS DEM FELRLEAEQKVVFSPGQYFMVDVPELGTRAYSAA NPVDGNTLTLIVKAVPNGKVSCALANETIETLQLDGPY GLSVLKTADETQSVFIAGGSGIAPMVSMVNTLIAQGYE KPITVFGSRLEAELEAAETLFGWKENLKLINVSSSVVG NSEKKYPTGYVHEIPEYMEGLLGAEFYLCGPPQMINSV QKLLMIENKVPFEAIHFDRFF</p>
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3.2 PROTPARAM tool analysis

PROTPARAM tool analysis helped us to predict the physical and chemical attributes of enzyme. TmoA is the largest subunit with 500 amino acids and TmoB was the smallest one with 84 amino acids. TmoA is followed by TmoE, TmoF, TmoC and TmoD with 327, 326, 112 and 103 number of amino acids, respectively. The molecular weight of these components ranged between 9587.99 - 58103.54.

Three subunits, TmoE (5.57), TmoA (5.20), TmoB (5.25) and TmoF (5.16) exhibited the highest pI values. Highest instability index was found in case of TmoD, TmoE and TmoB. i. e., 49.67, 47.77 and 41.98, respectively. The aliphatic index ranged between 95.73 and 66.80. All the subunits showed negative values for GRAVY ranging between -0.054 to -0.637 (Table 2).

Table 2: Prediction of physicochemical properties of components of T4MO using PROTPARAM tool

Component	No. of amino acids	Molecular weight	Isoelectric point (pI)	Instability index	Aliphatic index	GRAVY
TmoA	500	58103.54	5.20	39.27	66.80	-0.518
TmoB	84	9587.99	5.25	41.98	89.17	-0.114
TmoC	112	12325.73	4.38	27.78	77.41	-0.253
TmoD	103	11618.09	4.46	49.67	95.73	-0.359
TmoE	327	38346.28	5.57	47.77	74.92	-0.637
TmoF	326	35983.30	5.16	34.57	91.84	-0.054

3.3 SOPMA tool analysis

Alpha helix of T4MO subunits was highest in TmoA (291) and lowest in TmoC (6). In TmoF, 74 amino

acids were part of extended strand while in TmoE, the number of these amino acids was lowest. i. e., 6.

Random coil ranged between 194 and 34 for TmoA and TmoB, respectively (Table 3).

Table 3: Prediction of secondary (2D) structure of components of T4MO using SOPMA tool

Component	Alpha helix (%)	Extended strand (%)	Random coil (%)
TmoA	291 (58.20)	15 (3.0)	194 (38.80)
TmoB	28 (33.33)	22 (26.19)	34 (40.38)
TmoC	6 (5.36)	36 (32.14)	70 (62.50)
TmoD	36 (34.95)	21 (20.39)	46 (44.66)
TmoE	215 (65.75)	6 (1.83)	106 (32.42)
TmoF	89 (27.30)	74 (22.70)	163 (50.00)

3.4 ALPHAFOLD: 3D configuration analysis

The prediction of 3D configuration of proteins by ALPHAFOLD revealed highest level of complexity in TmoA, TmoE and TmoF (Figure 2). While TmoB and TmoC and TmoD demonstrated least complex folding.

3.5 MEME SUITE Analysis

The six conserved motifs detected in case of TmoA were RMSGHMG, HHSYHMG, PSVCNM, PGNRNM, QTDESRHAQ and MMDELRHGQ with p-values 1.38e-9, 2.26e-9, 4.92e-9, 1.43e-8 And 2.77e-11, Respectively. In case of TmoB, six motifs identified were, AYHCVN, AESGLN, NDSMDQ, KDFLVQ, PRDMTI and PREGCM with p-values of 1.21e-8, 2.05e-7, 1.02e-7, 2.18e-7, 1.41e-7 And 3.23e-7, respectively. In TmoC, VKAYQAM, VITCRAH, LDDIWV, GDDIYV, LWTFND and METFET motifs were found with p-Values 2.67e-9, 3.14e-9, 7.48e-8, 5.43e-7, 1.30e-8 and 6.58e-7, respectively. In TmoD, domains identified included RKTLEEQLGRPFNM, MSTLADQALHNNNV, YFDKTM, SFAGQL, DRRAYN and DLVEPV. The p-values of these motifs were 1.08e-15, 8.29e-15, 2.73e-8, 6.48e-7, 3.64e-7 and 5.09e-7, respectively. In TmoE, VIEGWI, VREGWE, TISNCC, TMARCY, TAFDWG and TYPDAG motifs were identified with p-values 2.66e-9, 2.78e-8, 5.04e-9, 4.44e-8, 7.21e-9 and 1.28e-7, respectively. In case of TmoF, CGPPQM, CGACKI, KYPTGYVH, KVPFEAIH, KVPFEAIH, MFNIQSDD and HFEADSND domains were predicted with p-values 2.51e-8, 4.03e-8, 1.33e-10,

Figure 2: Prediction of three dimensional (3D) configuration of T4MO components based on SWISSMODEL

TmoA (B) TmoB (C) TmoC (D) TmoD (E) TmoE (F) TmoF

7.27e-10, 1.70e-10 and 5.19e-10, respectively (Table 4 And Figure 3).

Table 4: Prediction of conserved motifs of components of T4MO enzyme based on MEME suite

No.	E-value	p-value	Motif sequence
TmoA			
1	5.2e+000	1.38e-9	YVTEEQLFPE RMSGHMG IPLEKWESYD
2		2.26e-9	DLFLKDIDEL HHSYHMG VWYWRTTAWW
3	6.4e+000	4.92e-9	RMDLVSPETL PSVCNM SQIPLVGVPG
4		1.43e-8	EGRMARFSKA PGNRNM ATFGMMDEL R
5	3.2e+001	2.77e-11	YTFANLISSI QTDESRHAQ QGGPALQLLI
6		2.77e-11	PGNRNMATFG MMDEL RHGQ LQLFFPHEYC
TmoB			
1	6.4e+000	1.21e-8	DSMDQVAEKV AYHCVN RRVAPREGVM
2		2.05e-7	TELFPRDMTI AESGLN PTEVIDVVFE
3	5.7e+001	1.02e-7	FLVQLVVVDL NDSMDQ VAEKVAYHCV
4		2.18e-7	SAFPVHAAFE KDFLVQ LVVVDLNDSM
5	1.9e+002	1.41e-7	VRKHRSTELF PRDMTI AESGLNPTEV
6		3.23e-7	AYHCVNRRVA PREGCM RVRKHRSTEL
TmoC			
1	7.5e+000	2.67e-9	VLIVNSEEHG VKAYQAM CPHQEILLSE
2		3.14e-9	LLSEGSYEGG VITCRAH LWTFNDGTGH
3	1.7e+002	7.48e-8	MSFEKICS LDDIWV GEMETFETSD
4		5.43e-7	CLAEYPVEVK GDDIYV STKGILPNKA
5	9.7e+001	1.30e-8	EGGVITCRAH LWTFND GTGHGINPDD
6		6.58e-7	CSLDDIWVGE METFET SDGTEVLIVN
TmoD			

1	1.2e+001	1.08e-15	IAAEGELILT RKTLEEQLGRPFNM QELEINLASF
2		8.29e-15	MSTLADQALHNNNV GPIIRAGDLV
3	3.1e+001	2.73e-8	IQADEDQIRF YFDKTM
4		6.48e-7	NMQELEINLA SFAGQI QADEDQIRFY
5	1.4e+002	3.64e-7	DNPGKEITVE DRRAYN RIAAEGELIL
6		5.09e-7	NNVGPIIRAG DLVEPV IETAEIDNPG
TmoE			
1	3.2e+000	2.66e-9	HALEPNDNA VIEGWI EKWRPLADRA
2		2.78e-8	QFNEREHDQM VREGWE HTMARCYSPL
3	4.3e+000	5.04e-9	AYVQQMAPAS TISNCC ILQTADSLRW
4		4.44e-8	DQMVREGWEH TMARCY SPLRYLFHCL
5	3.7e+001	7.21e-9	GLRELMEKQL TAFDWG EAFVSLNLVV
6		1.28e-7	TAYRTHELSL TYPDAG LGEHERELWE
TmoF			
1	8.0e+001	2.51e-8	EGLLGAEFYL CGPPQM INSVQKLLMI
2		4.03e-8	VFPYECNSGG CGACKI ELLEGEVSNL
3	1.1e+002	1.33e-10	SSSVVGNSEK KYPTGYVH EIPEYMEGL
4		7.27e-10	SVQKLLMIEN KVPFEAIH FDRFF
5	5.7e+001	1.70e-10	MFNIQSDD LLHHFEADSN
6		5.19e-10	FNIQSDDLH HFEADSND TLLSAALRAE

Figure 3: Prediction of conserved motifs, their locations and consensus of T4MO components based on MEME suite

4. Discussion

T4MO enzymes has previously been characterized for analysis of its crystal structure, functional study and for synthesis of chiral sulfoxides (Feingersch et al. 2008, Lountos et al. 2005). However, this is the first ever study documenting in-silico characterization of this enzyme. Among the subunits of T4MO, T4moD is the most crucial for catalysis as it binds TmoA

subunit and serves as catalytic effector. TmoB and C are associated with electron transfer (Hemmi et al. 2001).

The pI of protein affects its stability, activity, solubility, folding patterns and modifications (Schuurmans Stekhoven et al. 2008). TmoA, B, E and F exhibit slightly acidic character as compared to TmoC and D. Instability index below 40 shows stability of protein (Gamage et al. 2019). Hence, TmoB, D and E were found stable while TmoA, F and C were unstable. Aliphatic index is directly related with thermal stability of protein. TmoD was the highly thermostable followed by TmoF and TmoB. TmoA was the least thermostable. The less thermostable components may be engineered through modification of amino acids of their hydrophobic core (Ikai 1980). All the components of enzyme were hydrophilic with negative GRAVY values indicating their increase solubility in polar solvents.

Alpha helix content of proteins corresponds to the stability, DNA interactions and folding of membrane proteins. Only TmoA and E exhibited significant alpha helix character showing their more stable character and tendency of forming transmembrane domain (Li et al. 2019). The extended strand content represents tendency of enzyme catalysis and protein interactions of enzyme (Eswar et al. 2003). Only TmoF demonstrated good percentage of extended strand indicating its capacity of interacting other proteins.

Conserved motifs are the short sequences of amino acids that assist in understanding protein functions, its binding tendencies and active sites location. These sites may also be targeted to enhance the functioning of protein through engineering. All the subunits of T4MO documented in current study were found to exhibit the conserved motifs.

Current investigation enabled us to explore the different components of T4MO enzyme at structural, physical and chemical levels. This information might be exploited in future for the modification of enzyme for better toluene bioremediation, via genetic engineering. To enhance the stability of this enzyme, its unstable domains (TmoA, F and C) as well as conserved domains should be targeted.

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